

WAYS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical foundations of the development of the professional-creative competence of future teachers, in particular, the current issues, are studied. Also, theoretical-methodological aspects and tasks of increasing students' creativity and creativity were analyzed.

Key words: professional activity, training, component, empirical, pedagogical feature, methodology, competence, creative, professional.

INTRODUCTION

The level of competence of pedagogues is important in education of a comprehensively developed personality. In the science of pedagogy, the concept of psychological-pedagogical competence means the pedagogue's achievement of the highest level of results in the educational process, high professional potential, as well as communication and positive qualities. The word "competence" is defined by having awareness, reputation, comprehensive understanding and experience in one's field. Competence is a personal quality, and it is an ability, knowledge, skills and competence expressed in pedagogical activity and social life in different situations. The goals of improving the knowledge, skills, and qualifications of students of higher education institutions in the world, developing their intellectual maturity, increasing the quality of education, humanizing it, introducing healthy technologies into the educational system, continuity and continuity, development and socialization tasks are being set to provide, increase the creativity of specialists, including the creativity of training. The main goal of modern education is to prepare a person who is fully developed for society and the state, socially adaptable to society and work, and who can work on himself.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Issues of formation and development of teacher's professional-creative competence V.A. Adolf, T.G. Braje, E.F. Zeera, I.A. Zimnyaya, N.V. Kuzmina, M.I. Lukyanova, A.K. Markova, A.M. Novikova, G.S. Trofimova, G. Bernhard, V. Bloom, H. Markus, It has been studied by many philosophers, pedagogues and psychologists such as R.Sterner.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The process of education and upbringing consists in preparing the growing young generation for life based on the social order that reflects the demands of society. In the process of education and training, young people acquire the knowledge, manners, customs, culture and labor skills collected by their ancestors, take their rightful place in society based on life experience, and the personality of a pedagogue in the formation of their potential and outlook. his professional skills are important. At the same time, the formation of qualities necessary for solving new issues and problems arising from the demands of the times in young people is a priority task of the field of pedagogical activity.

Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level.

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work.

It is no exaggeration to say that competence and competence are one of the concepts that live in harmony with a person throughout his life and activities. Competence is knowledge, suitability for the profession, competence, experience, leadership. Competence is the ability to demonstrate one's abilities and talents in any activity.

Professional competence is evident in the following cases:

- in complex processes;
- performing unclear tasks;
- using conflicting information;
- being able to have an action plan in an unexpected situation.

Competence of a teacher - inculcating knowledge, suitability for the profession, competence, experience, responsibility in leadership activities. To be a master of one's field, of one's work, means to know the secrets of one's field in depth in every way.

Stages of formation of pedagogical competence:

- Ability determination
- Education and formation
- Exercise (giving small tasks)
- Trust (appointment to an independent leadership position)
- The peak of leadership

Uzbek pedagogic scientists are among those who expressed many opinions about the concept of competence. Among them, B. Khodjayev, A. Musurmanova, N. Saidahmedov, A. Muslimov, E. Yuzlikaeva, R.D. Riskulova, A.E. Kenjaboyev in their scientific research works and practical methodical articles use modern pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process in a continuous educational institution. competence of teachers and the didactic demands placed on it, expressed their opinions about the essence of this term and its components.

The problem of competence and its types have been the subject of research not only by us, but also by scientists from the CIS countries. There are different approaches to the classification of types of competence. Including N.A. Muslimov and M.B. From the point of view of professional education, Orozova divides competencies into 5 types.

Professional competence means the breadth of a specialist's worldview, his business skills and personal qualities, his ability to make the right decisions based on his knowledge, skills and qualifications. In order to improve the professional competence of a teacher of higher education, it is necessary to ensure the continuity of practical training along with theoretical training. Theoretical and practical training of preschool teachers is based on the following didactic principles, regardless of organizational forms and methods:

- Integration of theoretical and practical knowledge;
- Systematically improving professional knowledge and skills;
- Functional connection with future professional and pedagogical activities:

- Demonstration of students' practical activities;
- The formation of a sense of responsibility and the desire to gradually work independently in connection with one's professional activity;
- Formation and development of competence as a result of improving theoretical and practical knowledge and skills of future teachers.

The stages of formation of professional competence are as follows:

- Self-analysis and understanding of the necessary things;
- Self-development planning, goal setting;
- Self-presentation and correction of shortcomings.

Pedagogical competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills, skills necessary for the implementation of pedagogical practice by a pedagogue and their practical application at a high level. Self-work and self-development are important in acquiring this competence. The analysis of the modern approach to the quality of education shows that in general education schools students should study and learn throughout their lives, regularly increase their knowledge and experience independently, and be able to solve problems in everyday life using life experience. being able to create a database, to be able to choose the main ones and to be able to analyze them are effective factors. The issue of competence and its place in society are the subject of many debates.

The teacher's acquisition of high professional skills is carried out directly through the continuous education system. Professional development, which occupies the main place in the continuous education system, allows to analyze the student's activity and give him prospective directions. The current era requires a teacher to correctly understand the requirements of advanced pedagogical technology of teaching, to be proactive, to be aware of the news in his subject and to be able to introduce it into his classes.

CONCLUSION

Understanding the basic elements of universal competence in the field of education is one of the main problems of modern pedagogy. Regarding the issue of basic competence, there are many opinions on the application of the experience of world pedagogues or the determination of competence criteria based on the norms of traditional Uzbek pedagogy, and there are still many unresolved issues. If we look at the scientific research conducted in this regard, we notice that a lot of attention is paid to various fields and specialties, the development of science, teaching methods, and technologies. But it can be noted that the issue of understanding these pedagogical methods and applying them in practical activities has become one of the most urgent problems.

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